

Generalization of partitions $P(n,k)$ with the admission of null or negative addenda

Introduction

While Bell numbers, which tell us the number of ways in which n objects can be distributed in n cells, admit empty cells, partitions $P(n,k)$, although related to Bell numbers, traditionally do not admit zero. Here an extension of partitions $P(n,k)$ is presented, where one or more addenda can be null or even negative.

Notation:

$P(n,k) = m$ means that there are m different ways of writing n as the sum of k non-zero addenda. The order of the addenda does not matter. Each way is called a "part" of the partition.

$PZ(n,k)$ indicates a partition where the zero addendum is allowed.

$P1(n,k)$ indicates a partition where, in addition to zero, addendum -1 is also allowed.

We could go on...

N.B. $P(a,b) = P(c,d)$ means that the two partitions have the same number of parts, parts that are not necessarily equal. This also applies to $PZ(n,k)$, $P1(n,k)$ and so on.

• Recurrences

It is well known¹ that for $P(n,k)$ the following recurrence holds:

$$P(n,k) = P(n-k,k) + P(n-1,k-1) \quad (1)$$

It is usually used for the calculation of $P(n,k)$ (assuming $P(0,0)=1$), from which, iterating on the second part on the right (done explicited in Appendix 1) we obtain the relation

$$\sum_{i=1}^k P(n-k,i) = P(n,k), \text{ which can also be written in the form } \sum_{i=1}^k P(n,i) = P(n+k,k) \quad (1 \text{ bis})$$

which will be most useful in the generalization of $P(n,k)$ to include null or negative addenda.

For example, for $n=5$ and $k=3$ we have $P(8,3) = P(5,1) + P(5,2) + P(5,3) \rightarrow 5 = 2 + 2 + 1$

We immediately note that for partitions with null or negative addenda, the recurrence (1) does not apply. For example,

$$PZ(10,3) \neq PZ(7,3) + PZ(9,2)$$

where, as seen in Table A,

$$PZ(10,3) = 14, \quad PZ(7,3) = 8 \text{ e } PZ(9,2) = 5 \quad (8+5 = 13 \neq 14)$$

¹ Stanley Richard. Enumerative combinatorics. Vol. 1, Ch. 1, Sec. 17. Cambridge University Press, 2012.

However, the basic recurrences for these generalized partitions can be obtained by increasing by one unit the sum of the addenda n in the second part to the right of the recurrence, as shown in Appendix 2. These changes are also justified, as will be seen, in the construction of $PZ(n, k)$, $P1(n, k)$, $P2(n, k)$ etc.

Therefore, we get the recurrences:

$$P(n, k) = P(n - k, k) + P(n - 1, k - 1) \quad (1)$$

$$PZ(n, k) = PZ(n - k, k) + PZ(n, k - 1) \quad (2)$$

$$P1(n, k) = P1(n - k, k) + P1(n + 1, k - 1) \quad (3)$$

$$P2(n, k) = P2(n - k, k) + P2(n + 2, k - 1) \quad (4)$$

More generally, the recurrence is:

$$Pm(n, k) = Pm(n - k, k) + Pm(n + m, k - 1)$$

where $Pm(n, k)$ are the partitions that allow integer addenda $0, -1, -2, -3, \dots -m$.

For example, from (2) we have:

$$PZ(10, 3) = PZ(7, 3) + PZ(10, 2) \text{ which, as shown in Table A, is } 14 = 8 + 6$$

Iterating on the second part (to the right) of recurrences (2), (3) and (4) gives, respectively:

$$PZ(n, k) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} PZ(n - k + i, k - i) \quad (5)$$

$$P1(n, k) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P1(n - k + 2i, k - i) \quad (6)$$

$$P2(n, k) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P2(n - k + 3i, k - i) \quad (7)$$

For example, from (5) we have:

$$PZ(10, 4) = PZ(6, 4) + PZ(7, 3) + PZ(8, 2) + PZ(9, 1) \text{ this is, from Table A, } 23 = 9 + 8 + 5 + 1.$$

In fact, for (2) we have $PZ(10, 4) = PZ(6, 4) + PZ(10, 3)$ where, always for (2), we have:

$$PZ(10, 3) = PZ(7, 3) + PZ(10, 2) \text{ and } PZ(10, 2) = PZ(8, 2) + PZ(10, 1) \text{ and } PZ(10, 1) = 1$$

- **Calculation of $PZ(n, k)$ and $P1(n, k)$ values**

From the recurrences, remembering that, obviously, $Pm(1, 1) = 1$ and $P(0, 0) = 1$, it is possible to derive the values of the generalized partitions. As an example, Table A shows the values of $PZ(n, k)$ for n and k from 0 to 10.

Table A. $PZ(n,k)$

$n \backslash k$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
3	0	1	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
4	0	1	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
5	0	1	3	5	6	7	7	7	7	7	7
6	0	1	4	7	9	10	11	11	11	11	11
7	0	1	4	8	11	13	14	15	15	15	15
8	0	1	5	10	15	18	20	21	22	22	22
9	0	1	5	12	18	23	26	28	29	30	30
10	0	1	6	14	23	30	35	38	40	41	42

Note that for $k = n$, $PZ(n, n)$, this partition is $P(n)$. These values are on the diagonal of the Table and remain constant to the right of the diagonal.

As an example of use of the recurrence (2) we have:

$$PZ(7,5) = PZ(7,4) + PZ(2,5) \rightarrow 13 = 11 + 2$$

Table B (below) shows the values of $P1(n,k)$ for k from zero to 10 and n from -2 to 10. Note that the rows in the table for n null or negative are the values of $P(m)$ where $m = (k + n)$.

For example, for $n = -1$ and $k = 6$, we have $P(6 - 1) = P(5) = 7$.

Table B. $P1(n,k)$

$n \backslash k$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
-2	0	0	1	1	2	3	5	7	11	15	22
-1	0	1	1	2	3	5	7	11	15	22	30
0	1	1	2	3	5	7	11	15	22	30	42
1	0	1	2	4	6	10	14	21	29	41	55
2	0	1	3	5	9	13	20	28	40	54	75
3	0	1	3	7	11	18	26	38	52	73	97
4	0	1	4	8	15	23	35	49	70	94	128
5	0	1	4	10	18	30	44	65	89	123	164
6	0	1	5	12	23	37	58	82	116	157	212
7	0	1	5	14	27	47	71	105	146	201	267
8	0	1	6	16	34	57	90	131	186	252	340
9	0	1	6	19	39	70	110	164	230	318	423
10	0	1	7	21	47	84	136	201	288	393	530

As an example of the recurrence (3) we have:

$$P1(5,7) = P1(-2,7) + P1(6,6) \rightarrow 65 = 7 + 58$$

Table C shows the values of $P2(n,k)$ for k from zero to 10 and n from -4 to 10.

Table C. $P2(n,k)$

n/k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
-4	0	0	1	2	5	10	20	38	70	123	212
-3	0	0	1	3	6	13	26	49	89	157	267
-2	0	1	2	4	9	18	35	65	116	201	340
-1	0	1	2	5	11	23	44	82	146	252	423
0	1	1	3	7	15	30	58	105	186	318	530
1	0	1	3	8	18	37	71	131	230	393	653
2	0	1	4	10	23	47	90	164	288	488	807
3	0	1	4	12	27	57	110	201	352	598	984
4	0	1	5	14	34	70	136	248	434	732	1204
5	0	1	5	16	39	84	163	300	525	887	1455
6	0	1	6	19	47	101	199	364	638	1076	1761
7	0	1	6	21	54	119	235	436	764	1291	2112
8	0	1	7	24	64	141	282	522	919	1549	2534
9	0	1	7	27	72	164	331	618	1090	1845	3015
10	0	1	8	30	84	192	391	733	1297	2194	3590

As an example of the recurrence (4) we have:

$$P2(7,9) = P2(-2,9) + P2(9,8) \gggg 1291 = 201 + 1090$$

Note that $P2(-n,n) = P(n)$

• **Construction of $PZ(n,k)$, $P1(n,k)$, $P2(n,k)$**

$PZ(n,k)$ can be constructed using $P(n,i)$ for i ranging from 1 to k and adding zeros until having the required k addenda. For example, $PZ(7,3)$ is constructed using:

$$P(7,1) = 7$$

$$P(7,2) = 61, 52, 43$$

$$P(7,3) = 511, 421, 331, 322$$

Adding zeros we have:

$$\underline{7\ 0\ 0} \text{ from } P(7,1)$$

$$6\ 1\ 0$$

$$5\ 2\ 0$$

$$\underline{4\ 3\ 0} \text{ from } P(7,2)$$

$$5\ 1\ 1$$

$$4\ 2\ 1$$

$$3\ 3\ 1$$

$$\underline{3\ 2\ 2} \text{ from } P(7,3)$$

Thus, we have all the parts with sum equal to 7 and admitting zero.

The proof that operating as shown above generates all and only the parts that admit zero and have sum n is obtained noting that $PZ(n,k)$ can also be built starting from $P(n+k,k)$ and removing 1 from all addenda, as seen in the example of $PZ(7,3)$ below.

Thus there is a one-to-one correspondence between the number of parts of $PZ(n,k)$ and $P(n+k,k)$, where $P(n+k,k)$ is obviously complete.

The number of parts of $PZ(n,k)$ can be calculated from its components $P(n,i)$ using (1bis).

$$PZ(n,k) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n,i) = P(n+k,k) \quad (8)$$

For example, $PZ(10,4) = P(10,1) + P(10,2) + P(10,3) + P(10,4) = P(10+4,4) = 23$ or even

$$PZ(7,3) = P(10,3) = 8$$

Example of construction of $PZ(7,3)$ obtained from $P(10,3)$ by removing 1 from all addenda.

$P(10,3)$ is:

8 1 1	<u>7 0 0</u> from $P(7,1)$
7 2 1	6 1 0
6 3 1	5 2 0
5 4 1	<u>4 3 0</u> from $P(7,2)$
6 2 2	5 1 1
4 3 2	4 2 1
4 4 2	3 3 1
4 3 3	<u>3 2 2</u> from $P(7,3)$

• Similarly, $P1(n,k)$ can be constructed using $PZ(n,i)$ ($i=1,k$) and adding -1 where addenda are less than k .

Therefore, we get: $P1(n,k) = \sum_{i=0}^k PZ(n+i, k-i)$

For example, $P1(6,4) = PZ(6,4) + PZ(7,3) + PZ(8,2) + PZ(9,1)$ which, for Table A, holds $9+8+5+1=23$

Therefore, we have the table as follows:

$P1(6,4)$

6	0	0	0
5	1	0	0
4	2	0	0
3	3	0	0
4	1	1	0
3	2	1	0
2	2	2	0
3	1	1	1
2	2	1	1
7	0	0	-1
6	1	0	-1
5	2	0	-1

4	3	0	-1
5	1	1	-1
4	2	1	-1
3	3	1	-1
3	2	2	-1
8	0	-1	-1
7	1	-1	-1
6	2	-1	-1
5	3	-1	-1
4	4	-1	-1
9	-1	-1	-1

where the first nine parts are due to $PZ(6,4)$, the following eight parts to $PZ(7,3)$, the next five parts to $PZ(8,4)$ and the last part to $PZ(9,1)$. Note that

$$PZ(6,4) = P(6,1) + P(6,2) + P(6,3) + P(6,4) = P(10,4) = 9$$

$$PZ(7,3) = P(7,1) + P(7,2) + P(7,3) = P(10,3) = 8 \text{ and}$$

$$PZ(8,2) = P(8,1) + P(8,2) = 5$$

$$\text{So, } P_1(6,4) = P(10,4) + P(10,3) + P(10,2) + P(10,1) \rightarrow 23 = 9 + 8 + 5 + 1$$

Note that $P_1(6,4)$ can also be obtained from $P(14,4)$ removing 2 from all its elements.

$$P(14,4) = 23 \rightarrow P_1(6,4) = 23$$

11	1	1	1	9	-1	-1	-1
10	2	1	1	8	0	-1	-1
9	3	1	1	7	1	-1	-1
9	2	2	1	7	0	0	-1
8	4	1	1	6	2	-1	-1
8	3	2	1	6	1	0	-1
8	2	2	2	6	0	0	0
7	5	1	1	5	3	-1	-1
7	4	2	1	5	2	0	-1
7	3	3	1	5	1	1	-1
7	3	2	2	5	1	0	0
6	6	1	1	4	4	-1	-1
6	5	2	1	4	3	0	-1
6	4	3	1	4	2	1	-1
6	4	2	2	4	2	0	0
6	3	3	2	4	1	1	0
5	5	3	1	3	3	1	-1
5	5	2	2	3	3	0	0
5	4	4	1	3	2	2	-1
5	4	3	2	3	2	1	0
5	3	3	3	3	1	1	1
4	4	4	2	2	2	2	0
4	4	3	3	2	2	1	1

This table coincides, apart from the order of the parts, with the previous table of $P1(6,4)$.

- Similarly, $P2(n,k)$ is constructed. For example $P2(6,3) = 19$ can be constructed starting from $P(6+3*3,3) = P(15,3)$ and removing 3 from all addenda.

$P(15,3) \rightarrow P2(6,3) = 19$

13	1	1	10	-2	-2
12	2	1	9	-1	-2
11	3	1	8	0	-2
11	2	2	8	-1	-1
10	4	1	7	1	-2
10	3	2	7	0	-1
9	5	1	6	2	-2
9	4	2	6	1	-1
9	3	3	6	0	0
8	6	1	5	3	-2
8	5	2	5	2	-1
8	4	3	5	1	0
7	7	1	4	4	-2
7	6	2	4	3	-1
7	5	3	4	2	0
7	4	4	4	1	1
6	6	3	3	3	0
6	5	4	3	2	1
5	5	5	2	2	2

- In summary, we have the following formulas that are very useful in evaluating the value of these generalized partitions:

$$PZ(n,k) = P(n+k,k) \quad (8 \text{ bis})$$

$$P1(n,k) = PZ(n+k,k) = P(n+2k,k) \quad (9)$$

$$P2(n,k) = P1(n+k,k) = P(n+3k,k) \quad (10)$$

For example, from Tables A, B and C we have:

$$\begin{aligned} PZ(7,3) &= P(7+3,3) = P(10,3) = 8 \\ P1(8,4) &= PZ(8+4,4) = P(8+2*4,4) = P(16,4) = 34 \\ P2(6,4) &= P1(6+4,4) = P(6+3*4,4) = P(18,4) = 47 \end{aligned}$$

In general we have:

$$Pm(n,k) = P(n+(m+1)*k,k)$$

Note that in $Pm(n,k)$ n can be less than k or even negative, and the partition has a positive value.

For example, from Table B we have:

$$P1(-1,3) = P(5,3) = 2$$

Appendix 1

The equation (1) is:

$$P(n, k) = P(n - k) + P(n - 1, k - 1)$$

$$\text{but } P(n - 1, k - 1) = P(n - k, k - 1) + P(n - 3, k - 2)$$

$$\text{and } P(n - 2, k - 2) = P(n - k, k - 2) + P(n - 3, k - 3)$$

$$\text{and } P(n - 3, k - 3) = P(n - k, k - 3) + P(n - 4, k - 4)$$

and so on, until $P(m, 0) = 0$

For example, let $n = 7$ and $k = 4$, we have:

$$P(7,4) = P(3,4) + P(6,3)$$

$$P(6,3) = P(3,3) + P(5,2)$$

$$P(5,2) = P(3,2) + P(4,1)$$

$$P(4,1) = P(3,1) + P(3,0)$$

Appendix 2

The recurrence (1): $P(n, k) = P(n - 1, k - 1) + P(n - k, k)$ is well known.

(A simple proof of this relationship is given in: math.stackexchange.com/questions/1908701)

$$\text{By construction and remembering (1bis), we obtain equation } PZ(n, k) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n, i) = P(n + k, k) \quad (\text{A})$$

For example, $PZ(7,3) = P(10,3) = 8$ (see Table A).

$$\text{From (A), of course, we have } PZ(n - k, k) = P(n, k) \quad (\text{B})$$

For example, for $n = 15$ and $k = 6$, from (1) we have: $P(15,6) = P(14,5) + P(9,6) \rightarrow 26 = 23 + 3$

Using (B) this equation becomes:

$$PZ(15 - 6,6) = PZ(14 - 5,5) + PZ(9 - 6,6) = PZ(9,6) = PZ(9,5) + PZ(3,6) \rightarrow 26 = 23 + 3$$

This can be generalized to have $PZ(n - k, k) = PZ(n - 1 - (k - 1), k - 1) + PZ(n - k - k, k) =$

$$= PZ(n - k, k - 1) + PZ(n - k - k, k)$$

This relation, setting $m = n - k$, can be rewritten as $PZ(m, k) = PZ(m, k - 1) + PZ(m - k, k)$ which is the relation (2) sought.

Similarly, (3) and (4) are justified.